

Table 1: Parade Trappings on Stand-Alone Wooden Horses, 1627

Description of the Trappings	Historical Connection	Chamber	Wooden Horse	Notes (on the Trappings)
With turquoises and garnets (lost)	1610. Gift from Emperor Rudolf II to Christian II	Second saddle chamber (“Cammer neben der Stuben gegen der Rennbahn”)	A black horse, called <i>Der Schleicher</i> Portrait of the horse presented by Emperor Rudolf II to Christian II in 1610	In place by 1615 Tack and caparison substituted before 1627 with gift by Polish envoy Removed before 1699, probably in 1695
Made in Prague by Johann Michael, inv. no. L 1	1610. Christian II’s visit to Emperor Rudolf II	First saddle chamber (“Stube gegen der Rennbahn”)	A red (i.e. chestnut) and white horse	In place by 1615
With turquoise and garnet imitations (lost, formerly inv. no. L 5)	1617. Gift from Janusz Radziwiłł to Johann Georg I	Türkische Kammer (“Ungerische Cammer”)	A “bluish” (i.e. grey) horse Portrait of the horse presented by Janusz Radziwiłł to Johann Georg I in 1617	In place after 1618
Ottoman, with turquoises, rubies and nephrite, inv. nos. L 2, L 235, L 514	1617. Gift from Emperor Matthias to Johann Georg I	Easternmost terrace room (“Althan Stuben gegen dem Naumarckt”)	A grey “Turkish” horse	
Ottoman, with turquoises and nephrite, inv. nos. L 3, L 236, L 447	1620. Gift from Emperor Ferdinand II to Johann Georg I	Jägerkammer	A brown horse called <i>Der schöne König</i> Portrait of the horse presented by Emperor Ferdinand II to Johann Georg I in 1620	In place before 1624

Table 2: Parade Trappings on Stand-Alone Wooden Horses, 1699

Description of the Trappings	Historical Connection	Chamber	Wooden Horse	Notes (on the Trappings)
Made in Prague by Johann Michael, inv. no. L 1	<p>1610. Christian II’s visit to Emperor Rudolf II</p> <p>1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong</p>	Gute Sattelkammer	A horse painted in red (i.e. chestnut) and white	Probably used by Augustus the Strong at a festival in February 1697
With turquoise and garnet imitations (lost, formerly inv. no. L 5)	1617. Gift from Janusz Radziwiłł to Johann Georg I	Neue Inventionskammer	<p>A black horse, called <i>Der Schleicher</i></p> <p>Portrait of the horse presented by Emperor Rudolf II to Christian II in 1610</p>	
Ottoman, with turquoises, rubies and nephrite, inv. nos. L 2, L 235, L 514	1617. Gift from Emperor Matthias to Johann Georg I	Kurkammer	A grey “Turkish” horse	
Ottoman, with turquoises and nephrite, inv. nos. L 3, L 236, L 447	1620. Gift from Emperor Ferdinand II to Johann Georg I	Jägerkammer	<p>A brown horse called <i>Der schöne König</i></p> <p>Portrait of the horse presented by Emperor Ferdinand II to Johann Georg I in 1620</p>	
Silver- and gold-embroidered, with tassels (lost)	1666. Wedding of Johann Georg III in Copenhagen	Dritte Büchsenkammer	A painted wooden horse	In place from 1684 to 1709
Made by Abraham Schneider, with rock crystal gems, inv. no. L 13	1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Maultier-Gegatter	<p>A horse “painted in the fashion of an ermine”, called <i>Merseburger</i></p> <p>Portrait of the horse ridden by Augustus the Strong at the entry procession into Cracow in 1697</p>	<p>Used by Augustus the Strong at a festival in 1695</p> <p>In place since 1699. From 1695 to 1697 in the <i>Spießpagenkammer</i>, probably on the horse called <i>Der Schleicher</i></p>

With pearls and diamonds, inv. no. L 8	1693. Wedding of Augustus the Strong 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Spießpagenkammer	A piebald horse Portrait of the horse ridden by Augustus the Strong at the ceremony of the Homage in Cracow in 1697	In place since 1699
Bought in Italy in 1601-1602; enamelled, enhanced with rubies, inv. nos. L 7, L 610	1693. Wedding of Augustus the Strong 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Andere Büchsenkammer	A brown horse called <i>Rechenberger</i> Nothing is known on the horse portrayed	In place since 1699
With yellow glass gems (“topazes”) in gilt brass fittings, inv. nos. L 33, L 129	1693. Wedding of Augustus the Strong 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Türkische Kammer	A “bluish” (i.e. grey) horse Portrait of the horse presented by Janusz Radziwiłł to Johann Georg I in 1617	In place from 1699 to 1710
With green glass gems (“emeralds”) in gilt brass fittings, inv. no. L 116	1693. Wedding of Augustus the Strong 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Zeuggegatter	An “egg-yolk yellow” horse	In place from 1699 to 1709
Tack with gem-studded silver-ribbon bows, inv. no. L 151 ; unconnected saddle and caparison (lost)	1686. Gift by Christian of Saxe-Weißenfels to Johann Georg III (tack) 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Pistolenkammer	A grey horse (“Blauschimmel”)	In place from 1699 to 1709

Table 3: Parade Trappings on Stand-Alone Wooden Horses, 1709-1710

Description of the Trappings	Historical Connection	Chamber	Wooden Horse	Notes (on the Trappings)
Made in Prague by Johann Michael, inv. no. L 1	1610. Christian II's visit to Emperor Rudolf II 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Gute Sattelkammer	A horse painted in red (i.e. chestnut) and white	
With turquoise and garnet imitations (lost, formerly inv. no. L 5)	1617. Gift from Janusz Radziwiłł to Johann Georg I	Neue Inventionskammer	A black horse, called <i>Der Schleicher</i> Portrait of the horse presented by Emperor Rudolf II to Christian II in 1610	
Ottoman, with turquoises, rubies and nephrite, inv. nos. L 2, L 235, L 514	1617. Gift from Emperor Matthias to Johann Georg I	Kurkammer	A grey "Turkish" horse	
Ottoman, with turquoises and nephrite, inv. nos. L 3, L 236, L 447	1620. Gift from Emperor Ferdinand II to Johann Georg I	Jägerkammer	A brown horse called <i>Der schöne König</i> Portrait of the horse presented by Emperor Ferdinand II to Johann Georg I in 1620	
Made by Abraham Schneider, with rock crystal gems, inv. no. L 13	1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong 1709. Used by Augustus the Strong at the <i>Carrousel of the four Continents</i>	Zeuggegatter	An "egg-yolk yellow" horse	Tack refashioned in 1709 and combined with the "emerald"-studded saddle originally pertaining to inv. no. L 116
With pearls and diamonds, inv. no. L 8	1693. Wedding of Augustus the Strong 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Spießpagenkammer	A piebald horse Portrait of the horse ridden by Augustus the Strong at the ceremony of the Homage in Cracow in 1697	

Bought in Italy in 1601-1602; enamelled, enhanced with rubies, inv. nos. L 7, L 610	1693. Wedding of Augustus the Strong 1697. Coronation of Augustus the Strong	Andere Büchsenkammer	A brown horse called <i>Rechenberger</i> Nothing is known on the horse portrayed	
With crystal sun ornaments on head and crupper, inv. no. L 12	1709. Used by Augustus the Strong at the <i>Parade of the Gods</i> and nightly tilting at the ring	Maultier-Gegatter	A horse “painted in the fashion of an ermine”, called <i>Merseburger</i> Portrait of the horse ridden by Augustus the Strong at the entry procession into Cracow in 1697	New tack combined with the rock crystal-studded saddle originally pertaining to inv. no. L 13
Lined with silver fabric, with coloured gems, inv. nos. L 156, L 599, L 484	1709. Used by Frederick IV of Denmark at the <i>Parade of the Gods</i> and nightly tilting at the ring	Dritte Büchsenkammer	A dark brown horse	
With openwork silver fittings on mother-of-pearl plaques, inv. no. L 4	1709. Used by Frederick IV of Denmark at the <i>Carrousel of the four Continents</i>	Pistolenkammer	A black horse	Made in 1709 combining two earlier sets of trappings
Ottoman parade trappings used at the coronation of Stanisław Leszczyński (Warsaw, National Museum)	1710. Captured from Stanisław Leszczyński	Türkische Kammer	Probably: a “bluish” (i.e. grey) horse Portrait of the horse presented by Janusz Radziwiłł to Johann Georg I in 1617	